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Annotation: As Kaikovus himself pointed out, a whole work is dedicated to the education of young men described in the last chapter. Kaykovus said "... I wrote all my thoughts and concepts in a book for you, and I knew every science, every craft and every fish, I explained them all in forty-four chapters", the life experience of every young person's mental, moral, and physical education. described the ways and methods of bringing to maturity in connection with .

Key words: "Quran" and "Hadith", young men, King Gilon.

The fate and development of the country is closely dependent on the education of the youth. Their well-rounded development is the main factor that ensures the stability of the country's future. Today, when different cultures and ideologies are fighting, our children, who are stepping into an independent life, who have just started to distinguish white from black, are able to fully understand their identity and fall on their right paths, especially when they are older. ' people's life experience is very useful.

A large part of spiritual education is derived from spiritual values, including the teachings of our ancestors. These advices and teachings are reflected in the writings in the books that have been left to us. A truly educated reader can easily distinguish a book from others, which is able to raise his spirituality by content. Reading books of this content is like enjoying the conversation of virtuous scholars. In particular, Kaikovus's "Nightmare" can be included among the books with such a content. Unfortunately, today many of our young people are not aware of the contents of this book, which is evident when some young people blindly, unknowingly and without understanding follow the "mass culture", we are telling the truth .

The content of this book is that King Kaikovus wants to educate his son Gilon the king with his life experiences, and he says that his advice is the most valuable inheritance for his son. In his work "Nightmare", he addresses his son Gilon Shah and says: "O child, I hope that you will accept these advices. As you know, the Russian custom of the people is that they run around, search and find something from the world and leave their things to their loved ones. I created these words in the world , you are the most precious treasure for me. The time of my journey is near, I have placed before you what I have produced from the world, so that you do not build a house for yourself and do not do things that are not suitable for you.

In the work "Nightmare" by Shah Kaikovus, issues of education and morality occupy the main place. The book consists of 44 chapters. The author expresses a very important point in the chapter " About respecting parents", in which he uses a popular saying of our people: "What you sow, you will reap". According to him , if a person does good to people, respects the elders, and is kind to the little ones, his good deeds will return from others, and even if he does bad deeds, his deeds will definitely return to himself from others.

Kaikovus advises his son again in this chapter: "... if you want your child to respect you, you should also respect your parents, because the way you treat them, the same way you treat yourself Come back." With this, he urges not to upset the parents , to respect them and be polite with the sweet talker.

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Kaikovus instructs his son to be close to the people and look after their interests: " See a lot of the little good of the people , learn what is close to the interests of the people."

the book "Nightmare" by Kaikovus, the theory of education in the following areas, which must be acquired by young people, is provided:

1. About getting knowledge.
2. About professions and various professions.
3. About the rules of life and conduct.
4. About physical maturity.

Because it is necessary for every young person to have body, soul , passion and maoni, that is, kindness, enlightenment, and wisdom, and these qualities are mentioned in the above four directions. Kaikovus points out that each person possesses the following ten qualities mentioned by Pythagoras. These are: not to fight with someone superior to oneself; do not sit in the middle of the congregation with an envious person: do not be friends with a hypocrite, hypocrite: do not deal with a liar: do not talk to a miser; not to drink wine with strangers, enemies ; not to sit together with wives; not to tell secrets to people; if someone tells you your fault, try to get rid of this fault; do not praise someone too much or abuse too much ; not to threaten a person in need with grudge and anger; to forgive the sin of the sinner ; to be kind to the little ones; gives life recommendations such as not to order the same work to two people, that a person is like this every minute of his life

Emergence of educational and moral views

It is known that during the Eastern Renaissance, the main issue in the spiritual and educational sphere was the human problem . That is why great attention is paid to educational issues. Didactic works are characteristic of the East the leading idea was the problem of moral and spiritual maturity of a person, and a higher level of advancement. Humanity, the idea of glorifying a person is considered the main core of the works related to education. As the main means of implementing this idea, that is, the idea of humanity, it is important to implement education that leads to formation of high moral habits, human relations and qualities. Because high moral qualities are expressed in the idea of humanity, the educational-ethical direction became important in the philosophy and pedagogy of the Eastern Renaissance. The issue of ethics has been the center of attention of philosophers, great thinkers, historians, poets and writers alike . Educational and moral treatises were published , both theoretical and practical issues of ethics were analyzed. Yusuf Khos such as "Kutadgu Bilig", "Akhlaqi Nasiri", "Qabusnama", "Hibbat ulhaqaiq", "Gulistan", "Bo'ston", "Akhlaqi Jalali", "Akhlaqi Muhsini", "Mahbub ul-Qulub" The educational and moral works of Hajib, Nasiriddin Tusi, Kaikovus, Ahmed Yugnaki, Muslihiddin Sa'di, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Jaloliddin Davani, Husain Vaiz Koshifiy were created in the field of solving the problem of spiritual and moral formation of the human personality that we mentioned above. important as purely pedagogical works. In these educational and moral works, the idea was put forward that a person's spiritual maturity can be achieved only on the basis of mastering science. Because since the period we are referring to, teaching literacy has been carried out along with the study of the "Quran" and "Hadith" and the assimilation of their instructions. Accordingly , the teachings of the "Qur'an" and "Hadith" influenced the work of both scientists and writers. The reason for the influence of hadiths is the special emphasis on universal human qualities. The important features of Islam put forward in them: honesty, generosity, devotion, kindness, charity, shame, seeking knowledge, rules of conduct, moral standards, etc. , are expressed and are reflected in the literature of the East , including educational and moral works. affected. Educational and

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moral works were created directly on the basis of the ideas put forward in Hadiths. The influence of hadiths began with Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig" and was based on Kaikovus' "Qabusnoma", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibbat ul-haqaiyiq", Saadi's "Gulistan", Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub ul-Qulub" and other works. 'looks. Both the idea, the content, and the form are proof of this. For example, in "Qur'an", "Hadith", and educational and moral epics, along with the definition of science, the rules of conduct and manners of life are explained. behavior, rules of conduct are based on Islamic principles, the similarity of the contents of educational and ethical works depends on the spiritual ground on which they are based.

Kaikovus pays special attention to education in his work, and considers education to be one of the factors that shape the human mind and personal life. In this, he promotes the elevation of the human spirit to the heights, searches for the causes of negative evils. In particular, he considers it his duty to recognize that education has a high influence in life. In his opinion, the goal of educating young people is to make them not only today, but also for the future. Therefore, the author pays special attention to the behavior and actions of young people in the work. He also covered issues such as how to treat a friend and an enemy. As it is said from the beginning of the child, it is necessary to educate the child from birth, to teach moral standards, to make the child skilled in science, to develop the child's skills for work, otherwise "late" upbringing will have no effect. , said that it will not give the necessary effect. In the "Nightmare" it is emphasized that it is the right time to spend all your energy on getting knowledge and learning a profession.

Taking into account the above, our young readers will essentially enrich their spirituality by reading works of this content in their free time. Today, many opportunities have been created for young readers, they can read and understand the works they want in the electronic version. Peace and prosperity of the society in the future depends, first of all, on the education and training of our youth. In any household, neighborhood, and family where upbringing is well established, that household, neighborhood, and family will be blessed if they know and maintain harmony. By itself, the prosperity and freedom of the country will be strengthened and will continue to rise.

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